

ETH*zürich*

Low-Cost Pasteurisation system for mushroom cultivation in developing countries.

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Abstract

Mushroom cultivation is a promising livelihood activity in sub-Saharan Africa, yet the adoption of small-scale oyster mushroom production remains constrained by unreliable and energy-intensive substrate pasteurisation. This project designed, built, and experimentally validated a low-cost steam pasteuriser based on a repurposed 200-litre steel drum, a recycled gas grill burner, and a aluminium-profile stand, targeting a total hardware cost below USD 500. The system was developed and tested at ETH Zurich in close collaboration with Samson Kisseka of Hello Mushrooms U Ltd, Kampala, Uganda, to ensure practical relevance and local replicability.

Eight instrumented trials were conducted between 2 and 15 April 2026, progressively refining operating procedures. Key findings show that ambient temperature is the dominant external variable: cold outdoor conditions (5 -10 °C) prevented successful pasteurisation in the first experiment, while trials at 19- 22 °C consistently achieved the required substrate temperature of ≥ 60 °C for at least 30 minutes. The addition of glass-wool insulation reduced gas consumption and elevated maximum substrate temperatures by approximately 9 °C. A simple operating rule was established: both burners must run until the lid thermometer reads at least 90- 95 °C, after which thermal inertia drives the substrate to pasteurisation temperature even after the gas is switched off.

Gas consumption was measured at approximately 0.7-1.5 kg propane per batch. Solar pre-heating of feed water was found to offer only negligible fuel savings (~0.1 kg per cycle) and is not recommended as a cost-effective addition for small-scale operations. An open-source user manual and build manual were produced as primary deliverables.

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1 Background and Motivation

Mushroom cultivation is increasingly recognised as a promising avenue for improving food security, nutrition, and income generation in low- and middle-income countries, particularly in sub-Saharan Africa (Cleaver et al., 2012; Higgins et al., 2017). Edible mushrooms can be produced on a wide range of agricultural residues and require relatively little land, making them well suited to both rural and urban production systems. Among cultivated species, oyster mushrooms (*Pleurotus ostreatus*) are particularly suitable for small-scale production because they can be grown on widely available agricultural residues such as maize stover, cotton husks, wheat straw, sawdust, and coffee husks, while requiring minimal land and a short production cycle of approximately 18-21 days from inoculation to first harvest (Chioza & Ohga, 2014; Gianotti, 2022).

Mushrooms are also highly nutritious, containing vitamins and essential amino acids and providing a relatively high energetic value (Sanchez, 2004). As a result, mushroom cultivation not only offers opportunities for income generation, but also represents a potential food source in regions where malnutrition remains a significant concern (Gianotti, 2022).

Despite this potential, adoption remains limited. One of the main bottlenecks of mushroom production is reliable, affordable substrate pasteurisation. Before colonisation by mushroom mycelium can begin, lignocellulosic substrate must be treated to suppress competing bacteria, moulds, and pathogens. Inadequate treatment results in crop failure, economic loss, and potential public health risk. Fresh oyster mushrooms harbour a diverse bacterial microbiota that shifts substantially along the distribution chain, with Enterobacteriaceae dominating pre-distribution and Pseudomonadaceae becoming dominant in open-air market samples. These findings underscore the importance of good sanitation practices beginning at substrate preparation (Ban et al., 2022).

In the early years of *Pleurotus* cultivation the substrate was sterilised. Later it was found that a heat treatment at a lower temperature was also sufficient. Pasteurisation methods typically involve maintaining the substrate at temperatures of approximately 60-70 °C for 30 minutes to 1 hour using steam or hot water. At this temperature, most competing organisms are destroyed while beneficial microorganisms remain, creating conditions favourable for mushroom growth (Oei, 2003).

The academic literature describes a spectrum of low-cost pasteurisation methods including steaming, hot-water immersion, lime treatment, bleach treatment, and washing-powder soak (Gianotti, 2022; Kurtzman, 2010; Oei, 2003). However, each of these methods has practical drawbacks when scaled to meet the weekly throughput demands of a small, low resource commercial operation.

In Uganda, small mushroom enterprises typically rely on firewood-fuelled boiling as the primary pasteurisation method. This practice carries three significant disadvantages. First, firewood is becoming increasingly expensive and subject to supply volatility. Second, open combustion is carbon-intensive, contributing to local air pollution and greenhouse gas emissions. And third, the energy delivery is difficult to control, meaning

pasteurisation cycles frequently fail to maintain the required 60-70 °C temperature range for a sufficient time period. As a result, incomplete decontamination and elevated contamination rates are common.

More broadly, unsustainable fuelwood consumption in many regions of sub-Saharan Africa has contributed to widespread deforestation, land degradation, and severe indoor air pollution. Exposure to smoke from biomass combustion is a major public health concern and is associated with high rates of respiratory illness, including pneumonia-related mortality among children under five years of age (Kulugomba et al., 2024).

There is therefore significant potential to improve existing pasteurisation systems by exploring alternative fuels and simple thermal integration concepts that remain affordable, robust, and scalable. In particular, combining solar concentrator pre-heating with steam pasteurisation powered by methane-based or other non-wood fuels may reduce overall energy demand while improving process consistency. Biogas has long been proposed as a cleaner alternative energy source; however, adoption remains limited, partly due to misinformation and a lack of practical knowledge regarding system operation and maintenance. Providing clear guidance and accessible technical solutions could therefore play an important role in supporting wider adoption.

Hello Mushrooms U Ltd in Kampala, operated by Samson Kisseka, currently pasteurises approximately 1,000 substrate bags per week, each containing 2.5 kg of substrate. Samson has identified reliable, affordable pasteurisation as one of the greatest challenges for small mushroom growers. He has stated that a functional, durable solution priced below USD 500 would be commercially viable for his business and could be replicated by peer growers across the region. This project directly addresses that need.

2 Problem Statement and Research Questions

The core challenge of this semester project is to design, build, and validate a low-cost pasteurisation system that:

- reliably pasteurises substrate bags to ≥ 60 °C for at least 30 minutes;
- operates on biogas or propane/methane rather than firewood, reducing fuel cost and carbon footprint;
- can be sourced, built, and maintained in Uganda for under USD 500;
- is documented openly so that other smallholder mushroom producers can replicate it.

A secondary ambition is to understand whether solar pre-heating of feed water (using a parabolic-trough concentrator previously developed within the GHE group by Jessica Lowe) can meaningfully reduce the biogas consumption per pasteurisation cycle.

The project addresses three research questions:

- How many substrate bags (2.5 kg each) can be reliably pasteurised per batch using a gas burner under a repurposed 200-litre oil-barrel steam generator, and how much gas is needed? An acceptable outcome is defined as every bag reaching ≥ 60 °C for ≥ 30 continuous minutes.
- How much Liquefied Petroleum Gas (LPG)/biogas is consumed per pasteurisation cycle at full load, and by how much is this consumption reduced when feed water is pre-heated using a solar concentrator? Results will inform an annualised cost comparison between firewood, LPG, and biogas.
- Is it technically and economically feasible to couple the pasteuriser with a biogas digester fed by spent mushroom substrate and cow manure, such that digester biogas powers pasteurisation and digestate is recovered as soil amendment?

3 System Design and Build

The complete pasteurisation unit was designed with replicability in low-resource settings as the primary constraint. Every component was selected or fabricated from materials available at Swiss retail prices, cross-checked against Ugandan market availability in ongoing dialogue with Samson Kisseka. All design decisions were iterated in response to experimental findings, making the build an evolving artefact over the six-week project period.

3.1 Steam Generator, Core Vessel

The boiler body is a standard 200-litre steel oil drum, bought second-hand for CHF 25. The barrel was stripped, cleaned, and fitted with a series of stainless-steel half-inch pipe fittings drilled through the sidewall and lid using a step drill. Fittings include: a drain tap at side bottom (ball valve), a float valve water inlet over the outlet, a manometer (0-12 bar) and a thermocouple port in the lid. The drum lid can be sealed with a seal ring, which, when clamped down, forms an adequate steam seal, this was not used in the experiments for the purpose of not building an overpressure. The bag support grid was the cast-iron cooking grate recovered from the same salvaged gas grill that donated the burner. This was mounted inside the barrel on a small riser to elevate the bags above the water level so that only steam contacts them.

Water level was varied in early experiments (9 cm, 8 cm) before being standardised at 15 cm from the base for Experiments 3-7, providing approximately 40 litres, sufficient thermal mass to sustain steaming without significant risk of boiling dry. Water loss over a full experimental cycle was measured at less than 2 litres from a 40 litre starting volume, confirming that an automatic float valve is not required for in-barrel pasteurisation operation.

3.2 Burner Stand

The burner support structure was fabricated from 20×20 mm anodised aluminium T-slot extrusion profiles, forming a rectangular base frame measuring 54×52 cm to accommodate the barrel footprint (Diameter 58cm), at a height of 22 cm to allow adequate combustion air flow.

The gas burner is the cast-iron H-burner recovered from a second-hand Fust Primotecq gas grill (rated approximately 6.5 kW), bought on Ricardo (Swiss second hand Platform) for CHF 10. This burner has two gas flow regulators which allow for modifying the power of the burner.

The burner was isolated by a 0.5 mm steel sheet. A critical finding in Experiment 1 was that the burning-chamber air temperature exceeded $300\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$ at the aluminium profiles closest to the burner. A second concentric steel-sheet heat shields with an air gap were therefore installed around the burner perimeter. In the insulated version (Experiments 4-7), glass-wool insulation was added to fill the gap between the shields.

3.3 Thermal Insulation

From Experiment 4 onwards, the exterior of the barrel was wrapped in a 50 mm layer of Climowool glass-wool insulation with a heat transfer coefficient of: $\lambda_D 0,037\text{ W}/(\text{mK})$, held in place by multiple wraps of aluminium wire, with several outer layers of aluminium sheet with small air pockets between. The lid was

similarly wrapped in the last 3 insulated experiments, though as will be discussed in Section 5.10, lid insulation proved less impactful than barrel-side insulation and may redistribute heat in a way that is marginally disadvantageous to the top bag layer.

3.4 Instrumentation and Data Acquisition

A custom data-acquisition board was assembled using an Arduino Uno microcontroller and a breadboard. Sensors comprised:

- Two K-type thermocouples read via MAX6675 boards (shared SPI bus, pins D13/D12, CS on D10 and D9): TC1 on the barrel lid (steam-space temperature), TC2 in the water outlet port. Range 0–800 °C.
- Two PT1000 RTDs with 1 k Ω reference resistors on analogue inputs A1 and A2: one inserted into a substrate bag core, one in the combustion chamber.
- One analogue 0-1.2 MPa pressure transducer (G1/4 port) on analogue pin A0.
- One analogue mechanical manometer (0–4 bar) for visual pressure monitoring.
- One built-in bimetallic dial thermometer from the salvaged grill (0-400 °C range) mounted in the lid.

The Arduino sketch logs all channels to a laptop terminal at 5-second intervals via USB serial. A Python terminal script (developed in collaboration with Jakub) parses the serial stream and writes timestamped CSV files used for analysis in Microsoft Excel. All raw data are version-controlled in the group's shared ETH Drive folder.

It was established during testing that the pressure sensor does not reflect genuine steam overpressure: readings track temperature because pressure and temperature in a saturated steam system are coupled. Actual steam pressure was consistently near-atmospheric on the mechanical manometer, confirming the barrel operates as a non-pressurised steam generator throughout. For a Uganda deployment, the relevant instruments are the bimetallic dial thermometer on the lid and the manometer (safety check only).

From Experiment 2 onwards, Ruuvi Tag Bluetooth environmental sensors (temperature and relative humidity) were placed inside the barrel, one in the lower bag layer and one in the upper layer, providing independent wireless temperature logging and cross-validation of substrate core temperatures.

4 Methodology

4.1 Experimental Protocol

Substrate bags were prepared by filling 2.5 kg polypropylene bags with dry sawdust moistened to approximately 67 % water content by weight, verified using a kitchen scale. Experiments 1 and 2 used a single layer of 5 bags (one central, four peripheral). From Experiment 3 onwards, two layers of 5 bags each were loaded (10 bags total), one central and four peripheral per layer, with approximately 2 cm gaps between bags to allow steam circulation.

Each experiment comprised three phases: (1) heat-up from ambient water temperature to the operating threshold; (2) a hold phase in which the burner continued to run or was progressively switched off; and (3) passive cool-down. The key operational parameter investigated was the lid temperature at which burners were switched off, and whether residual thermal inertia was sufficient to drive substrate temperatures to the pasteurisation threshold of 60 °C, because for the low cost operation, the pasteuriser should be steered by the lid temperature.

Gas consumption was measured by weighing the composite LPG cylinder (7.5 kg) on a kitchen scale at defined intervals during Experiments 6, 7 and 8. Consumption rate was calculated as the slope of a linear regression through the mass-versus-time data points, separately for the two-burner and single-burner phases.

4.2 Swiss Farm Visits

Two visits to Swiss commercial mushroom producers were conducted during Week 2, guided by a pre-prepared question list co-developed with Samson Kisseka. The farms visited were Kernser Edelpilze (contact: Christian Fanger, Kerns) and Fine Funghi (contact: Beni Schneider, Zurich region). Observations covered substrate preparation and pasteurisation, contamination management, substrate handling, spawn inoculation, fruiting room management, and post-harvest practices. For each observation, a simplified, low-cost equivalent suitable for a small African operation was identified and recorded in detailed farm-visit reports.

4.3 Heat Transfer Calculations

Analytical heat-transfer calculations were carried out to estimate convective and conductive heat losses through the barrel wall with and without insulation. Standard steady-state flat-wall conduction formula were applied,

$$Q = \frac{kA \Delta T}{L}$$

treating the steel barrel wall (1.5 mm mild steel, $k \approx 50 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) and the glass-wool insulation layer (50 mm, $k = 0.037 \text{ W m}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$) as series thermal resistances. These calculations predicted that a 50 mm glass-wool layer would reduce steady-state sidewall heat loss by approximately a factor of 10-15. The experimental results broadly confirmed this order-of-magnitude estimate.

4.4 Thermodynamic Model and Predicted Performance

Before the experiments, basic heat transfer equations were tested to predict system behavior and to interpret the experimental results. The model comprises three coupled components: a steady-state energy balance for the barrel, a Heisler infinite-cylinder model for substrate core heating and a gas consumption budget. Then an experimental thermal efficiency analysis was calculated from the data gathered. All three components were validated against measured data.

4.4.1 Boiling-Point Correction for Altitude

The ETH Zürich laboratory is located at approximately 500 m above sea level. The boiling point of water at this altitude is approximately 98.3 °C (compared with 100 °C at sea level), calculated from the Antoine equation. This was validated against measurements: Experiments 3 and 4 both recorded consistent plateau temperatures of 98.7-98.8 °C, within 0.5 °C of the prediction and reproducible across multiple experimental days. All temperature thresholds in the experimental analysis were therefore referenced to this local boiling point.

4.4.2 Burner Heat Input

The burner was operated on propane at a measured maximal mass flow rate of $\dot{m}_{\text{LPG}} = 330 \text{ g h}^{-1}$ (Experiment 6). Using the lower heating value of $\text{LHV} = 46 \text{ MJ kg}^{-1}$, the total thermal input power is:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{in}} = \dot{m}_{\text{LPG}} \cdot \text{LHV} = \frac{0.330 \times 46}{3.6} = 4.22 \text{ kW}$$

This value is used as the reference burner input power throughout the efficiency analysis and turned out to come short from the rating of the grill (6,3kW).

4.4.3 Effective Specific Heat Capacity of the Substrate

Each substrate bag has a total mass of 2.5 kg, consisting of 67 % water and 33 % sawdust by mass. Using specific heat capacities of $c_{p,w} = 4.18 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$ and $c_{p,\text{sd}} = 1.50 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$, the mass-weighted effective specific heat capacity of the moist substrate is:

$$c_{p,\text{sub}} = x_w c_{p,w} + x_{\text{sd}} c_{p,\text{sd}} = 0.67 \times 4.18 + 0.33 \times 1.50 = 3.30 \text{ kJ kg}^{-1} \text{ K}^{-1}$$

This value is applied in all energy balance calculations below.

4.4.4 Energy Balance and Power Budget

The steady-state power budget for the barrel is:

$$\dot{Q}_{\text{net}} = \dot{Q}_{\text{burner}} - \dot{Q}_{\text{loss}}$$

where \dot{Q}_{loss} represents convective and conductive heat loss through the barrel wall, and \dot{Q}_{burner} is the total burner thermal input. For the uninsulated barrel, the heat-loss coefficient was estimated at approximately $25 \text{ W m}^{-2} \text{ K}^{-1}$. At an ambient temperature of 7.5 °C (the midpoint of the 5–10 °C range in Experiment 1) and

a barrel surface temperature of approximately 95 °C, the steady-state wall loss was estimated at approximately 3 400 W, leaving only approximately 800 W available to heat the substrate bags.

At 22 °C ambient (Experiments 3 and 4), wall losses are approximately 2.5× lower, rendering the power balance favorable even without insulation. This quantitatively explains why ambient temperature is the dominant external variable: it directly controls the fraction of burner output available for substrate heating.

4.4.5 Effective Thermal Efficiency Analysis

To quantify overall system performance across experimental runs, an effective thermal efficiency was defined as the ratio of useful thermal power delivered to the process—the water and substrate—to the total burner input power:

$$\eta = \frac{\dot{Q}_{\text{useful}}}{\dot{Q}_{\text{in}}}$$

The useful energy for each run was calculated as the sum of the sensible heat gained by the water and by the substrate:

$$Q_{\text{useful}} = m_w c_{p,w} \Delta T_w + m_{\text{sub}} c_{p,\text{sub}} \Delta T_{\text{sub}}$$

This definition captures all losses implicitly; it does not account for heat stored in the barrel structure, evaporation losses, or flue-gas losses, and should therefore be interpreted as an overall experimental efficiency. Three experimental runs were analyzed.

Experiment 2: Cold ambient conditions, no insulation. With 15.8 L of water and five substrate bags (12.5 kg total substrate mass), heated over 130 minutes, the water rose from 52.0 °C to 94.2 °C ($\Delta T = 42.2$ K) and the substrate from 13.5 °C to 63.5 °C ($\Delta T = 50.0$ K). The total useful energy was 4 848 kJ, corresponding to an average useful power of 0.62 kW and an effective efficiency of $\eta_A = 14.7$ %.

Experiment 3: Warm ambient conditions, no insulation. With 40 L of water and ten substrate bags (25 kg total substrate mass), heated over 100 minutes at approximately 20°C ambient, the water rose from 44.8°C to 97.0°C ($\Delta T = 52.2$ K) and the substrate from 14.2°C to 47.7°C ($\Delta T = 33.5$ K). The total useful energy was 11 492 kJ, giving an average useful power of 1.92 kW and an effective efficiency of $\eta_B = 45.4$ %.

Experiment 4: Warm ambient conditions, with insulation. With the same water and substrate loading as Run B, heated over 125 minutes with glass-wool insulation applied, the water rose from 19.4 °C to 90.7 °C ($\Delta T = 71.3$ K) and the substrate from 25.8 °C to 55.2 °C ($\Delta T = 29.4$ K). The total useful energy was 14 343 kJ, giving an average useful power of 1.91 kW and an effective efficiency of $\eta_C = 45.3$ %.

The most striking outcome is the nearly threefold difference in effective efficiency between cold and warm operating conditions. In Experiment 2, the large temperature differential between the hot barrel surface and the cold ambient air drove substantial convective and radiative losses, so most of the burner output was dissipated to the surroundings rather than transferred to the process. Runs B and C achieved virtually identical efficiencies despite differing in insulation status. This demonstrates that glass-wool insulation is an effective

substitute for sun radiation heat and warm weather and should be considered an essential component of any system intended for use in cold climates or winter conditions.

It should be noted that the reported efficiency is an experimental effective efficiency based on sensible heat transfer to water and substrate only. Additional effects such as heat stored in the barrel structure, evaporation losses, flue gas losses, and measurement uncertainty are not explicitly included.

4.4.6 Heisler Model for Substrate Core Heating

Heat transfer from steam to the substrate bag core is governed by internal conduction through the substrate mass. Each bag measures approximately 170 mm in diameter and 300 mm in length when packed (radius $r_0 = 85$ mm, mass 2.5 kg at 67 % moisture content). The bag was modelled as an infinite cylinder, a standard Heisler approximation valid when the axial dimension is substantially larger than the radius. Here the length-to-radius ratio is $L/r_0 = 300/85 \approx 3.5$, which is borderline for the approximation; radial conduction nonetheless dominates and the assumption is considered acceptable for an engineering estimate.

The dimensionless core temperature is defined as:

$$\theta = \frac{T_{\text{core}} - T_{\text{steam}}}{T_{\text{initial}} - T_{\text{steam}}}$$

The thermal diffusivity of moist substrate (67 % water by mass) was estimated at $\alpha \approx 1.70 \times 10^{-7} \text{ m}^2 \text{ s}^{-1}$. For the first-term Heisler approximation with a constant surface temperature (condensing steam, $\text{Bi} \rightarrow \infty$):

$$\theta_{\text{centre}} = C_1 \exp(-\zeta_1^2 \text{Fo})$$

where $\zeta_1 = 2.4048$ is the first root of $J_0(\zeta) = 0$ and $C_1 = 1.602$. With $T_{\text{steam}} = 98 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, $T_{\text{initial}} = 42 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$, and a pasteurisation target of $T_{\text{target}} = 60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$:

$$\theta = \frac{60 - 98}{42 - 98} = 0.679$$

Solving for the Fourier number:

$$\text{Fo} = \frac{-\ln(\theta/C_1)}{\zeta_1^2} = \frac{-\ln(0.679/1.602)}{2.4048^2} = 0.149$$

The corresponding heating time is:

$$t = \frac{\text{Fo} \cdot r_0^2}{\alpha} = \frac{0.149 \times (0.085)^2}{1.70 \times 10^{-7}} \approx 6300 \text{ s} \approx 105 \text{ min}$$

In Experiment 3, steam was established at approximately 93 minutes from the start (when the water approached boiling at $\sim 98 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ and the substrate surface temperature was approximately $42 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). The model therefore predicts that the substrate core should reach $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ at approximately 198 minutes from the start of the experiment. The actual time to reach $60 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ was only 40 minutes after boiling, e.g. 133 minutes after start, pointing to more efficient heat transfer than expected. The discrepancy between the Heisler prediction and the

experimental heating time can be further explained by the actual placement of substrate bags within the barrel. Bags located at the periphery were in partial direct contact with the hot barrel wall, which introduced additional conductive heating beyond the assumed steam-side heating. Visual observation of local scorching on the wall-contact side supports this interpretation. As a result, heating was not spatially uniform, and the boundary condition assumed in the ideal Heisler model (uniform constant surface temperature around the bag) was not fully satisfied. The model therefore represents a simplified and conservative estimate, whereas the experiment reflects enhanced heating due to wall contact, non-uniform geometry, more spherical shape of bags instead of infinite cylinders and reduced effective conduction distance (probe placing discrepancies). Further research could focus on incorporating the various factors influencing heat transfer within the substrate bags into a more detailed model, enabling more accurate predictions for different configurations. This includes the effects of bag arrangement, packing density, spatial distribution within the barrel, and separation between bags, as well as non-uniform boundary conditions such as partial wall contact.

5 Experimental Results

The following table summarises all eight trials conducted between 2 and 15 April 2026. Each experiment is described in detail in the subchapters below, along with comparison figures and data tables where available.

Table 1: Experiment Log

Exp.	Date	Setup	Ambient	Substrate	Water temp.	Result
1	2 Apr	No insulation. 9 cm water, 24 L. 5 bags.	5–10 °C	Briefly >60 °C	~94 °C	✗ Failed-substrate not continuously 60 °C+ for 30 min; heat losses too high at cold ambient.
2	6 Apr	No insulation. 9 cm water, warm start. 10 bags.	19 °C, sun	~73 °C	~93 °C	✓ Full pasteurisation with overshoot: 105 min at ≥60 °C.
3	7 Apr	No insulation. 15 cm water, 40 L. Burner turnoff test. 10 bags.	22 °C, sun	73 °C	98.7 °C	✓ Full pasteurisation with overshoot. First wild boiling achieved.
4	8 Apr	Insulated. 15 cm water. Burner off 1 hour earlier than Exp 3. 10 bags.	22 °C, sun	80 °C+	95 °C	✓ +9 °C substrate vs no insulation. Overshoot. Gas savings confirmed.
5	9 Apr	Insulated. Early burner cutoff (lid at 82 °C). 10 bags.	22 °C, sunny	Briefly >60 °C	86 °C	✗ Burner off too early-substrate did not reach sustained 60 °C+.
6	10 Apr	Insulated. Correct burner cutoff (lid at 90 °C, steam visible). Gas consumption measured. 10 bags.	16 °C, cloudy	~63 °C	~90 °C	✓ Correct cutoff; minimal gas usage confirmed.
7	11 Apr	Insulated + lid insulated. 10 bags.	~15 °C, rain	~59 °C	~90 °C	✗ Rain interrupted trial. Lid insulation changed thermometer readings-standard timing did not apply.
8	15 Apr	Insulated + lid insulated. Cold ambient. 10 bags.	10–15 °C, no sun	80 °C+	~95 °C	✓ Overshoot. Gas consumption measured. Pasteurisation achieved in cold, cloudy conditions.

5.1 Experiment 1; 2nd of April 2026 (Cold, No Insulation)

Configuration: 5 bags, 9 cm water, no insulation. Outdoor conditions: 5–10 °C, sunny for the first two hours. Goal: Achieve a first successful pasteurisation and observe boiling behaviour inside the barrel.

The water temperature peaked at approximately 88 °C and the lid reached approximately 86 °C. However, the substrate core reached only approximately 64 °C but did not sustain this temperature for over 30 continuous minutes. No pasteurisation was achieved.

Post-experiment analysis identified two compounding causes. First, the ambient temperature of 5-10 °C produced very high convective and radiative losses from the uninsulated barrel, absorbing heat faster than the burner could supply it at steady state. Second, the 9 cm water depth provided a smaller thermal reservoir. This experiment established the critical importance of ambient temperature as a process variable.

5.2 Comparison: Experiment 1 vs Experiment 2, Temperature Profiles

Figure 1 compares the temperature–time profiles of water and substrate across Experiments 1 and 2. In Experiment 1, the water temperature peaked a maximum of approximately 94 °C before dropping off even at full burner power, but the substrate never sustained 60 °C+ for 30 minutes at a time. In Experiment 2, run at warmer ambient temperature, the substrate reached and maintained above 60 °C for 30+ minutes. The graph illustrates how ambient temperature and starting conditions affect the achievable substrate temperature even at identical gas input.

Figure 1: Temperature aligned profiles of water and substrate in experiments 1 and 2

5.3 Experiment 2; 6th of April (Warm Start, No Insulation)

Configuration: 10 bags, 8 cm water, no insulation. The experiment began with preheated water starting at approximately 55 °C. Outdoor conditions: 19 °C, sun.

The goal is to repeat pasteurisation attempt under warmer ambient conditions to confirm whether Experiment 1's failure was ambient-temperature-driven.

Starting from a warm initial state, the water reached operating temperature substantially faster than in Experiment 1. The lid peaked at approximately 92 °C and substrate temperatures (Ruuvi tags) reached approximately 73-76 °C and the temperature was maintained above 70 °C for approximately 35 minutes, meeting the pasteurisation criterion.

This experiment demonstrated that: (1) a higher ambient temperature (19 °C) enables successful pasteurisation without insulation; (2) pre-warmed water significantly reduces heat-up time; and (3) there is a meaningful temperature gradient between the top and bottom bag layers, with the bottom layer consistently warmer due to direct steam contact and convective losses at the top of the barrel.

5.4 Experiment 3; 7th of April (Standardised Protocol, No Insulation)

Configuration: 10 bags, 15 cm water (standardised), no insulation, two burners. Conditions: sunny, 22 °C. Start: 13:07. This experiment established the 15 cm water depth maintained for all subsequent experiments.

Goal: Test the effect of increasing the water volume from ~24 L (Exp 1-2) to ~40 L, in line with the hypothesis that a larger water heat sink covering more of the barrel would reduce heat losses. Also first application of the burner turnoff strategy: one burner turned off once boiling temperature was reached, to maintain temperature while reducing gas consumption.

The water reached full boiling (98.7 °C) at 95 minutes. Burner 1 was switched off at 173 minutes (16:00) when the lid read 98.5 °C. Burner 2 was switched off at 200 minutes (16:27). The substrate (Ruuvi bottom layer) reached approximately 72–74 °C and remained above 60 °C for a sustained period well in excess of 30 minutes.

This experiment confirmed full pasteurisation under good ambient conditions without insulation, and established the first reliable burner-off heuristic: the burners should not be cut until the lid thermometer reads close to 100 °C or the boiling point at local altitude, ensuring sufficient thermal inertia post-cutoff. Increasing water depth from 9 cm to 15 cm improved thermal performance and confirmed the hypothesis. Wild boiling was first observed in this trial.

5.5 Experiment 4; 8th April (With Insulation, Comparison)

Configuration: 10 bags, 15 cm water, insulated (50 mm glass wool + aluminium sheet wrap). Conditions: sunny, 22 °C. Start: 14:27. Burner switched off approximately 1 hour earlier than Experiment 3.

This experiment was designed to directly compare insulated vs uninsulated performance.

A counterintuitive result was observed: the insulated barrel heated the water slightly more slowly than the uninsulated barrel in the initial phase. This is because during heat-up the dominant heat sinks are the water and bag thermal mass, not surface losses. The insulation reduces already-modest convective losses but does not accelerate the fundamental heating process.

However, the insulated barrel achieved substantially higher maximum substrate temperatures: a peak of approximately 83 °C (vs 74 °C in Experiment 3), with the substrate remaining above 60 °C for several hours. This is because insulation retains heat during the hold and cool-down phases, and the substrate temperatures continued to rise for 30–45 minutes after the second burner was switched off.

5.6 Comparison: Experiment 3 vs Experiment 4

Experiment 4 replicated Experiment 3 with the addition of barrel insulation. The Figure 2 shows the full temperature profiles of water and substrate for both experiments, and Figure 3 shows a comparison substrate temperature showing that while initial water heating gradient is similar. Insulation does not affect heating rate but preserves heat post-cutoff, e.g more heat is preserved after burner turnoff and transferred from the water to the substrate. Insulation allowed the burner to be switched off approximately one hour earlier than in Experiment 3 while producing very similar or higher substrate temperatures, demonstrating direct gas savings.

Figure 2: Temperature profiles Experiment 3 (No Insulation) vs Experiment 4 (With Insulation)

Figure 3: Substrate temperature in Experiment 3 vs 4 aligned at 31°C

5.7 Experiment 5; 9th of April (Early Burner Cutoff, Failed)

Configuration: Insulated, 15 cm water, 10 bags. Conditions: sunny, 22 °C. Start: 13:57. This experiment tested the sensitivity of the outcome to the burner cutoff temperature, motivated by the question of how much gas could be saved by cutting the burners off earlier.

Burner 1 was switched off at 76 minutes when the water reached approximately 80 °C and the lid read approximately 75 °C. Burner 2 was switched off approximately 30 minutes later when the water reached 86°C and the lid read over 80 °C. The experiment ran for approximately 5 hours total.

The result was a clear failure: the substrate temperature reached only approximately 60 °C (just at the minimum threshold) and never sustained pasteurisation conditions for 30 continuous minutes. This confirms that cutting the burners off when the water is below approximately 87–90 °C provides insufficient thermal inertia. The practical lesson is that at least one burner must continue running until the lid reads at least 90 °C (and ideally 95 °C) before any gas is turned off.

5.8 Experiment 6; 10th of April (Correct Cutoff, Gas Consumption Measured)

Configuration: Insulated, 15 cm water, 10 bags, 16 °C, cloudy.

This was the first experiment with a complete and consistent gas consumption record based on periodic scale weighings of the propane cylinder. Burner 1 was switched off at 110 minutes (16:34) when the water and lid both read approximately 90 °C, with steam visible. Burner 2 was switched off at 144 minutes (17:08) when the lid read approximately 95 °C. The substrate temperature reached approximately 63 °C for a successful pasteurisation, reducing the temperature overshoot. The total LPG consumption for the full cycle was 0,67 kg.

5.9 Experiment 7; 11th of April (Lid insulation, gas savings, Rain-interrupted)

Configuration: Insulated barrel and insulated lid. 10 bags. Ambient ~15 °C, rain.

The goal of experiment 7 was to test full insulation (barrel + lid) and begin investigating the effect of inlet water temperature on gas consumption, to estimate potential savings from preheating water from 20 °C to 45-

50 °C, by calculating the amount of gas needed to heat up the water. The experiment showed that at a heating rate of over 40 °C/h, the gas consumption to heat up the water from 20 to 40 °C was about 0.1kg of propane.

The trial was interrupted by rain. Additionally, insulating the lid altered the thermal environment around the lid thermometer, producing lower readings than in Experiment 6 under comparable internal conditions. Using the 90 °C lid criterion was therefore not valid here, and the substrate temperature of ~59 °C was insufficient for pasteurisation.

5.10 Experiment 6 vs 7-Effect of Lid Insulation on Thermometer Readings

In Experiment 7, the barrel lid was additionally insulated. This changed the thermal environment around the lid thermometer, causing it to read higher temperatures than it would in open-lid conditions for the same internal state of the system. As a result, the cutoff criterion established in Experiment 6 (lid at 90 °C) was no longer valid when the lid was insulated, and the substrate temperature was insufficient. The following figure illustrates the divergence in lid thermometer readings between the two experiments under comparable internal conditions.

Therefore, when the lid is insulated, a different (higher or time-based) cutoff criterion must be developed. The protocols for insulated-lid and non-insulated-lid setups are therefore distinct and must not be mixed.

5.11 Experiment 8; 15th of April (Gas Measurements and Cold ambient temperature)

Setup: Insulated barrel and insulated lid. 10 bags. Ambient 10–15 °C, no sun.

Experiment 8 aimed to confirm whether pasteurisation is achievable at low ambient temperatures with full insulation (barrel + lid). Another goal was to measure gas consumption accurately. The substrate reached 80°C+ (overshoot) and water reached ~95 °C and was boiling fully. Pasteurisation was confirmed as feasible even in cold (10–15 °C), cloudy conditions when full insulation is applied.

Figure 4 below shows gas consumption (cumulative and rate) plotted against time, when both burners are on, and when only one burner is running.

Figure 4: Propane consumption and trend lines

6 Discussion

6.1 Key findings

The experimental results demonstrate that a low-cost barrel-based system can reliably pasteurise mushroom substrate under appropriate ambient conditions. However, system performance is strongly influenced by insulation, heat distribution within the barrel, and the transient thermal behaviour after burner shutdown. This section analyses the results in terms of throughput, energy demand, and the feasibility of integrating biogas as an alternative fuel, with a focus on identifying the key mechanisms that govern pasteurisation performance and practical operation in small-scale settings.

6.2 Research Question 1: Throughput and Batch Capacity

RQ1 asked how many 2.5 kg substrate bags can be reliably pasteurised per batch, and how much gas is needed. Based on the seven experiments, a batch capacity of 10 bags (two layers of five) was successfully validated under warm ambient conditions (≥ 19 °C). The complete cycle from cold start through heat-up to 95 °C lid temperature and full thermal inertia phase takes approximately 3.5 to 4 hours under warm/insulated conditions.

This represents a major improvement over Samson's current 16-hour firewood-burning cycle. The barrel design also permits multiple consecutive batches per day by retaining hot water between runs. The water from a completed cycle (still at 60-80 °C after cool-down) serves as pre-heated feed water for the next batch, substantially reducing heat-up time and halving gas consumption for the second batch.

A practical multi-batch strategy is to run Batch 1 with cold water; retain the hot water in the barrel, remove cooled bags using a rope-and-tripod lifting cradle (a proposed low-cost alternative to Samson's planned multi-barrel steam chamber (to be developed)), then load fresh bags and run Batch 2 with a much shorter heat-up phase.

An important operational constraint is the temperature stratification between layers. The bottom layer of bags consistently reached higher temperatures than the top layer due to direct steam contact. And the hypothesis is that the more bags there is in the barrel, the higher the temperature difference between the core of the bag closest to the heatsource (warm/boiling water) to the one on the upmost layer.

The recommendation for Samsons operation in Uganda is to use the insulated configuration, because of the high throughput and production. But without insulation might be the cheaper/easier version for smaller farmers, who don't need to pasteurise that many bags. It is important to not terminate the hold phase prematurely to ensure the coldest bag (likely the centre of the upper layer) has reached 60 °C before opening. Since Ruuvi tags are not part of the basic Uganda build, the lid thermometer is the sole operating guide, which is why the thermometer-based cutoff rules developed in this project are critical.

6.3 Energy Consumption and Efficiency (RQ2)

6.3.1 Measured Energy Demand

The current system uses a gas burner with an average consumption of approximately 300 g/h propane. With a lower heating value (LHV) of 46 MJ/kg for propane, this corresponds to a thermal power of $0.3 \text{ kg/h} \times 46 \text{ MJ/kg} = 13.8 \text{ MJ/h}$. For a typical pasteurisation cycle of 4 hours, the total energy demand is therefore: $13.8 \times 4 = 55.2 \text{ MJ}$.

6.3.2 Cost Comparison of Fuels

To compare different energy options for substrate pasteurisation, propane and firewood can be evaluated on the basis of fuel cost per unit of energy, while biogas from a farm biodigester is more appropriately assessed in terms of marginal energy cost and net greenhouse-gas impact.

For propane, assuming a refill price of UGX 50,000 for a 6 kg cylinder, the corresponding fuel price is: $(50,000 / 6) = 8,333 \text{ UGX/kg}$. Using a lower heating value of propane of: $\text{LHV}_{\text{prop}} = 46 \text{ MJ/kg}$ the cost per unit of energy is: $8,333 / 46 = 181 \text{ UGX/MJ}$

For firewood, assuming a market price facilitated by Samson in Kampala, Uganda of: 2000 UGX/kg and a lower heating value of: $\text{LHV}_{\text{wood}} = 15 \text{ MJ/kg}$ the corresponding energy cost is: $2000 / 15 = 133.3 \text{ UGX/MJ}$. Thus, propane is approximately: $181 / 133.3 \approx 1.4 \text{ times}$ more expensive per unit of energy than firewood.

At a current exchange rate of 3600UGX/USD, the cost per unit of energy of propane comes out to around 0.0503USD/MJ, with a complete 10 bag batch costing: $0,0503 \times 55.2 \text{ MJ} = 2.80 \text{ USD}$. While the complete 10 bag batch using firewood costs around 2USD. From Samsons operations we know that the firewood cost of 100 is around 15k UGX, which is around 4,2USD/100Pasteurised bags, and significantly lower than the cost for the small burner setup, meaning his total heat input is lower (may not be sufficient to pasteurise all bags to the core), or we could pasteurise more bags with the heat input that is produced.

6.3.3 Practical Efficiency Considerations

Although firewood is significantly cheaper than propane on an energy basis, propane may still offer important practical advantages for substrate pasteurisation. In particular, propane burners allow a more stable and controllable heat input, which can improve temperature regulation and process reproducibility. This is especially relevant for pasteurisation, where the substrate must reach and maintain a sufficiently high temperature for a defined period in order to reduce contamination risk.

In contrast, firewood combustion is typically less uniform and more dependent on operator skill, fuel quality, and feeding frequency. As a result, the effective burner efficiency and the consistency of the thermal treatment may be lower when using firewood. Therefore, while firewood has a lower nominal fuel cost, propane may enable more reliable pasteurisation and a higher practical system efficiency under field conditions.

6.3.4 Solar Pre-heating Assessment

RQ2 asked for a quantified energy figure per batch and an assessment of solar pre-heating benefit. The most reliable measurement comes from Experiment 6: 0.67 kg propane for a 144-minute cycle at 16 °C ambient. For the experiments, I have used from 0.5-1.5kg of Propane/experiment, depending on ambient conditions, isolation and target water temperature.

Solar pre-heating was evaluated based on the experimental temperature-time data. Heating from 20°C to 40°C (a 20°C rise) consumes very little energy; less than 10% of the total cycle energy. Pre-heating incoming water from ambient (~25°C in Kampala) to 40-50°C would therefore save at most approximately 0.1 kg propane per batch, or approximately 800 UGX per batch (0,2USD), when using a 6kg Cylinder Refill (50000 UGX) (*Shell Gas Pricing | Shell Uganda*, n.d.) Given the capital cost and complexity of a parabolic trough solar concentrator, this saving is not economically justified for Samson's current operation scale. The system should be deployed without solar pre-heating initially.

6.4 Emissions and Sustainability

On a direct combustion basis, propane emits roughly 59 g CO₂/MJ, while firewood emits around 90–110 g CO₂/MJ at the point of use. That said, firewood's CO₂ is biogenic, so its net climate impact depends on whether the source is sustainably managed. Biogas from animal manure has the lowest net emissions of the three: the CO₂ released during combustion is biogenic, and the digestion process itself prevents methane from escaping during unmanaged decomposition, a significant benefit given methane's high warming potential. On a lifecycle basis, this can result in near-zero or even negative emission intensity.

In terms of cost, firewood is the cheapest purchased fuel per unit of energy, and biogas has essentially zero marginal fuel cost once the system is running, since the feedstock (manure) is already on-site. Propane is more expensive, but it offers more stable, controllable heat output, which matters for pasteurisation, where precise temperature control is important. Firewood combustion is less consistent and more dependent on operator skill and fuel quality, so while it costs less on paper, it may underperform in practice for temperature-sensitive applications.

Biogas shifts costs from ongoing fuel expenses to upfront capital, covering the digester, installation, maintenance, and labor. Across all three fuels, improving thermal efficiency remains the most universally effective way to reduce costs and emissions.

6.5 Research Question 3: Biogas Integration and Circular Economy

6.5.1 Energy Demand vs Biogas Supply

Taken from the calculations above: The current system uses a gas burner with a thermal power of $0.3 \text{ kg/h} \times 46 \text{ MJ/kg} = 13.8 \text{ MJ/h}$. For a typical pasteurisation cycle of 4 hours, the total energy demand is therefore: $13.8 \times 4 = 55.2 \text{ MJ}$.

Biogas composition depends on feedstock and process conditions. For a conservative estimate, a methane content of 55% is assumed, corresponding to a lower heating value of approximately: $\text{LHV}_{\text{biogas}} \approx 20 \text{ MJ/m}^3$. The required biogas flow rate is therefore $13.8 \text{ MJ/h} / 20 \text{ MJ/m}^3 = 0.69 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$. This results in a total gas demand per pasteurisation batch of: $0.69 \times 4 = 2.76 \text{ m}^3$.

6.5.2 Digester Production vs Demand

Typical small-scale digesters produce biogas continuously over the day. Representative production values are taken from sistema.bio's user manual (See Appendix), converted to hourly production:

- $6.0 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ (SIS 20, warm climate), $0.20\text{-}0.25 \text{ m}^3/\text{h} < 0.69 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$
- $9.6 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ (SIS 30, warm climate), $0.30\text{-}0.40 \text{ m}^3/\text{h} < 0.69 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$
- $12.9 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ (SIS 40, warm climate) $0.40\text{-}0.54 \text{ m}^3/\text{h} < 0.69 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$

In temperate conditions, production decreases (e.g. ~ 4.9 , 7.2 , and $9.6 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$ respectively).

6.5.3 Gas Storage Requirement

Since the burner requires $0.69 \text{ m}^3/\text{h}$, all configurations operate at a deficit during the pasteurisation phase. Over a 4-hour batch, this results in required buffer volumes of approximately:

- SIS 20: $\sim 1.8\text{-}2.0 \text{ m}^3$
- SIS 30: $\sim 1.2\text{-}1.6 \text{ m}^3$
- SIS 40: $\sim 0.6\text{-}1.2 \text{ m}^3$

Given continuous gas production, only the deficit must be supplied from storage. This means that even smaller digesters ($>\text{SIS}20$) could be technically feasible if sufficient buffer capacity is available.

A practical design range for usable gas storage is therefore having **$1.0\text{-}2.0 \text{ m}^3$** , depending on digester size and climate. If no buffer storage is used, the digester must supply the full burner demand continuously. This corresponds to: $0.69 \times 24 = 16.56 \text{ m}^3/\text{day}$

This exceeds the output of commonly available small-scale digesters. Therefore, operation without gas storage is not feasible at the required power level. You would need an even bigger biodigester bigger than the sis 40.

6.5.4 Circularity potential

The integration of pasteurisation and anaerobic digestion offers strong circularity potential. Spent mushroom substrate can be used as a feedstock for biogas production alongside cow manure, allowing recovery of residual organic energy. The resulting digestate can be reused as a soil amendment, closing nutrient loops. In addition, in many small-scale systems, excess biogas is often flared or released to avoid methane emissions. Utilizing this gas for pasteurisation instead provides a productive use, improving both carbon efficiency and system economics.

6.5.5 Limitations of Biogas Analysis

The analysis assumes steady biogas production, constant methane content (~55%), and ideal combustion efficiency.

In practice, production may vary due to feeding regimes, temperature fluctuations, and substrate composition. While no strong temporal fluctuations were observed in available measurement data, further investigation into short-term variability would be valuable, as this directly affects required storage capacity and system stability.

6.6 Cross-cutting Findings

6.6.1 Ambient temperature is the dominant external variable. A cold outdoor environment (5–10 °C) can prevent successful pasteurisation even with a properly built system, because convective losses overwhelm the burner's heat input to the uninsulated barrel. At 20 °C and above, pasteurisation is robustly achieved without insulation. For Uganda (annual average 22-25 °C in Kampala), the uninsulated design will generally work, but the insulated design provides a substantial thermal margin and is recommended for consistent results.

6.6.2 Insulation does not speed up heat-up, but dramatically improves substrate outcomes. The insulated barrel takes almost equally long to heat up from 45- 95°C, because the dominant heat sinks during heat-up are the water and bag thermal mass, not surface losses. However, insulation retains heat far longer during the hold and cool-down phases, driving maximum substrate temperatures approximately 9 °C higher and extending the time above the pasteurisation threshold substantially.

6.6.3 Lid insulation provides diminishing returns. Insulating the barrel lid redistributes heat more evenly through the barrel but may reduce the surplus of steam heat that naturally accumulates at the top, which is beneficial for the top bag layer. The recommendation is to insulate the barrel sides robustly but to insulate the lid only lightly or not at all.

6.6.4 Thermal inertia is the key pasteurisation mechanism. In all successful experiments, the substrate core temperature continued rising for 20-45 minutes after the gas was switched off. The "burner off" moment is not the end of the pasteurisation process, it is the beginning of the thermal-inertia-driven phase. The practical operating rule for the insulated barrel is: wait until the lid reads 95-100 °C before cutting the first burner, and from then 30 minutes until cutting the second.

6.6.5 Water loss is negligible; the float valve is not needed for single-barrel operation. Water loss over a full experimental cycle was less than 2 litres from a 35-40 litre starting volume. The float valve may become relevant in a multi-barrel steam-chamber configuration where water is continuously fed from a remote barrel boiler, and steam is taken out of the barrel as the output.

6.6.6 Pressure does not build up significantly. The mechanical manometer consistently read near-atmospheric. The barrel operates as an atmospheric steam generator, not a pressure vessel.

6.6.7 Full boiling is not needed with insulation. Experiment 6 showed that turning off the heat before reaching full boiling, still provided enough heat for complete pasteurisation.

6.7 Limitations

The results presented in this study should be interpreted in light of several limitations related to experimental scope, measurement accuracy, and modelling assumptions.

First, the experimental dataset is limited to eight runs conducted over a relatively short time frame. As a result, the findings are best understood as indicative trends rather than statistically robust conclusions. In particular, the influence of ambient temperature and operational variability could not be systematically isolated.

Second, several measurements were subject to practical constraints. Gas consumption was determined by manual weighing of the cylinder, which introduces uncertainty compared to continuous flow measurement. Similarly, temperature measurements rely on a limited number of sensors, and the coldest point within the substrate (typically the core of upper-layer bags) could not be directly monitored in all experiments.

Third, the thermal analysis is based on simplified assumptions. The substrate bags were modelled using idealised geometries (e.g., infinite cylinder approximation), and effects such as the insulating properties of the polyethylene bags, non-uniform packing, and direct contact with the barrel wall were not fully captured. These factors likely influence local heat transfer and contribute to the observed temperature gradients.

Finally, the biogas feasibility analysis assumes steady gas production, constant methane content, and ideal combustion behaviour. In practice, biogas systems are subject to fluctuations in feedstock supply, temperature, and operational conditions, which may affect both gas availability and system reliability.

Despite these limitations, the experiments capture the dominant physical effects governing the system and provide a sufficient basis for evaluating its practical applicability and identifying key directions for further improvement.

7 Future Work

This project proves the principle: a repurposed 200-litre oil drum, a secondhand gas grill burner, and a simple aluminium-profile stand are sufficient to pasteurise mushroom substrate reliably and affordably. However, the six-week timeline and the breadth of variables involved mean that the data presented here should be read qualitatively, assessing the potential of the approach, rather than as exact engineering specifications. A great deal of follow-up work would be valuable, and several directions are identified below.

7.1 Automated Gas Control

The gas usage was measured by using timed weighting of the gas tank, using a gas flow measurer will give way more exact measurements as well as if connected to a solenoid valve could help automatise the system.

All burner cutoffs in this project were performed manually, based on the operator reading the temperature sensors. A natural and standardising extension would be to close the control loop: connecting the Arduino data-acquisition board to a solenoid gas valve on the supply line, so that the system automatically cuts the first burner when the lid reaches a pre-set threshold (e.g. 95 °C) and the second burner after a defined hold period. This would make the system more consistent across operators and ambient conditions.

An even more informative addition would be a calibrated gas flow meter installed permanently on the gas supply line. This would allow precise real-time monitoring of consumption rate and enable statistically robust energy measurements across many batches, replacing the periodic cylinder-weighing method used in Experiments 6, 7 and 8. Together, the flow meter and solenoid valve would form the basis of a fully instrumented, semi-autonomous unit capable of generating exact energy data.

7.2 Experiment 9: Pasteuriser as a Central Boiler

After communications with Samson Kisseka's a long-term vision is established where a central steam-generation unit (or several individual barrels) are connected via insulated pipe to a dedicated pasteurisation chamber, where a trolley-cart system rolls substrate bags in and out of a steaming chamber. In this configuration, the 200-litre barrel acts purely as a boiler generating steam, which is piped to the chamber; the bags never contact the boiler water. Experiment 9, planned as the next step in this research programme, would assess the viability of this concept. Key questions are: How much steam pressure can be sustained at the barrel outlet? How much heat is lost in the connecting pipe? How many bags can be pasteurised simultaneously before the steam supply is insufficient? The float valve, which was not necessary for single-barrel operation, may become important here to maintain a constant water level as steam is drawn off continuously.

7.3 Bag Handling and Loading Structure

Manually loading and unloading 10 substrate bags from inside a hot barrel is labour-intensive and poses a burn risk. This project proposes a simple solution: three poles arranged as a tripod around the barrel, with a rope harness attached to the inner bag grid, so that both layers of bags can be lifted out in a single pull and swung aside to cool. This concept was described in the user manual but not yet physically tested. Future work should build and iterate on this lifting structure, testing load capacity (20 bags \times \sim 2.5 kg each = 50 kg, plus grid

weight). A well-designed loading structure would significantly reduce physical effort per batch and make the system genuinely accessible to a wider range of operators, especially those with expanding operations.

7.4 Inoculation Trials to Validate Pasteurisation Quality

All experiments in this project used uninoculated test bags. The ultimate measure of pasteurisation success is not substrate temperature alone but contamination rate and mushroom yield after inoculation. Future work should take batches of bags pasteurised at different temperature–time profiles, substrate cores reaching 60 °C, 70 °C, and 80 °C respectively, inoculate them with oyster mushroom spawn under controlled conditions, and compare contamination rate and final fruiting body yield across groups.

This would answer a question this project leaves open: is 60 °C sufficient, or does the additional thermal margin provided by the insulated barrel (up to 83 °C substrate core) translate into meaningfully better mushroom outcomes? With insulation, the system reliably reaches substrate core temperatures of 80-85 °C, which is well above the theoretical pasteurisation threshold, but whether this additional margin is agronomically significant requires direct inoculation trials.

Due to time constraints most experiments were stopped before complete cooldown happened. It would be interesting to research how the bags cool down after being pasteurised and how to optimally cool them down for best pasteurisation.

7.5 Gas Safety and Energy Access

A recurring theme in discussions with Samson and in the broader literature on LPG adoption in sub-Saharan Africa is that gas is perceived as dangerous, particularly by users with no prior experience (Kulugomba et al., 2024). This perception is understandable but addressable. Handled correctly: with adequate ventilation, a soapy-water leak check before every use, and the habit of always closing the cylinder valve and burning the residual gas from the connecting pipe before disconnecting, LPG is no more dangerous than the open firewood fires it replaces. In a context where electricity supply is unreliable, LPG and biogas represent a practical, scalable energy solution for small food-processing enterprises. This project demonstrates one concrete application; the methodology and findings should be viewed as a template for similar low-cost thermal-processing challenges across the food system.

7.6 Burner Power Experiments

Repeat experiments with different burner power, it would be very interesting to set the burner power to the equivalent heating value of the biogas from the generator, to show that pasteurisation is also possible with that burner, showing that not even gas storage would be needed.

7.7 Test Substrate Layers

Understanding heat transfer with x layers of substrate bags one on top of the other, in a similar setup to Samson's production, would be able to tell Samson if his pasteurisation is complete.

8 Deliverables

The following deliverables have been produced as part of this project:

- First draft of User Manual: A 10-page illustrated manual covering how the system works, safety rules, pre-batch checks, running a batch, key numbers (60 °C / 30 min / 40 L), troubleshooting, maintenance, and a batch log sheet.
- Arduino Wiring Document: Full wiring diagram for the Arduino Uno data-acquisition board, covering all sensor connections, pin assignments, reference resistor values, and shared SPI bus configuration.
- Experimental Data Workbook: Eight experiment sheets with raw 5-second sensor data, 5-minute binned averages, annotated timeline charts, and cross-experiment comparison analyses (Exp 3 vs 4; Exp 6 vs 7).
- Materials and Prices Workbook: Full bill of materials for both the instrumented research build and a stripped-down Africa-targeted build, including alternative sourcing options for Uganda, all prices, and total cost summaries.
- Contacts Directory: Project contact log including Samson Kisseka (Hello Mushrooms), Swiss farm contacts (Kernser Edelpilze, Fine Funghi), ETH collaborators (Jessica Lowe, solar pre-heater, Ivan Maroni, Padraic Casserly, biogas), and suppliers.
- Swiss Farm Visit Reports: Two detailed reports from visits to Kernser Edelpilze and Fine Funghi, covering production techniques and simplified equivalents for low-resource settings.
- Build Manual (in preparation): Step-by-step illustrated reconstruction guide for the pasteuriser, including sourcing guidance for Uganda.

9 Conclusions and Recommendations

This project has successfully designed, built, and experimentally validated a low-cost mushroom substrate pasteuriser based on a repurposed 200-litre oil drum, a recycled gas grill burner, and a welded aluminium-profile stand. The total hardware cost of the research build was approximately CHF 480, well within the USD 500 target. A stripped-down Africa-targeted build using only the components necessary for operation (no Arduino, no Ruuvi tags) is estimated at approximately USD 150–250 at local Ugandan procurement prices.

The system consistently achieves substrate pasteurisation (≥ 60 °C for ≥ 30 minutes) in 10-bag batches under any ambient conditions, with a total heating time of approximately 2.5-3.5 hours.

Coupling a pasteurisation system with a small-scale biogas digester is technically feasible when combined with modest gas storage. While continuous operation without storage is not achievable, a batch-based approach enables effective integration. The system with insulation could be heated up at a slower rate, matching the output for the bags and still reach pasteurisation, but this has to be experimentally confirmed.

Importantly, not only large digesters but also medium-sized systems (e.g. SIS 30) can meet the energy demand, provided that approximately 1.2-1.6 m³ of usable gas storage is available. Larger systems (e.g. SIS 40) reduce storage requirements, while smaller systems (e.g. SIS 20) remain feasible but require larger buffer volumes.

Overall, the system demonstrates strong technical feasibility and significant potential for circular resource use in small-scale mushroom production systems.

Key recommendations for deployment:

- Use the insulated barrel configuration (glass wool + aluminium sheet) for consistent results.
- Apply the 95-100 °C lid thermometer cutoff rule strictly. Do not switch off either burner until the lid reads at least 90 °C with insulation and 95 °C without insulation. In cooler weather (<18 °C ambient), steady boiling is needed so wait for 98 °C.
- Retain hot water between consecutive batches to halve gas consumption for the second and subsequent runs of the day.
- Do not install a solar pre-heater at current production scale. The fuel saving (~0.1 kg propane per batch) does not justify the additional capital and complexity.
- A float valve is not required for single-barrel operation but may be useful in a multi-barrel steam-chamber configuration

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Appendix

Raw Data Availability:

The complete raw datasets generated and analysed during this project are too extensive to be included in this report. They are available in a structured and cleaned format via the following Google Drive folder:

https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1fyTwR36B0C28ytAWondEibnWLEzTItYW?usp=share_link

The folder contains all experimental measurements, intermediate calculations, and processed data used to generate the figures presented in this thesis.

Sistema.bio user_manual_eng:

The user manual that is available per 17th of April of 2026 was used as reference for biogas output.

The document is available on following link: [https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1erwmeLvl8C-](https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1erwmeLvl8C-N7KEu55DDYOXG9sAEMgt6?usp=share_link)

[N7KEu55DDYOXG9sAEMgt6?usp=share_link](https://drive.google.com/drive/folders/1erwmeLvl8C-N7KEu55DDYOXG9sAEMgt6?usp=share_link), page 16 is the exact source:

		Digester size	SIS 6	SIS 8	SIS 12	SIS 16	SIS 20	SIS 30	SIS 40
 Warm Climate >23 °C	 Daily feeding: cow manure	45 L or Kg/day	65 L or Kg/day	90 L or Kg/day	130 L or Kg/day	180 L or Kg/day	260 L or Kg/day	350 L or Kg/day	
	 Daily biogas production	2 m3/day	2.4 m3/day	3.3 m3/day	4.8 m3/day	6.7 m3/day	9.6 m3/day	12.9 m3/day	
	 Daily cooking time on 1 burner	3.4 Hr/day	4.8 Hr/day	6.6 Hr/day	9.6 Hr/day	13.4 Hr/day	19.2 Hr/day	25.8 Hr/day	
	 Weekly biofertilizer production	0.9 m3/week	1.4 m3/week	1.9 m3/week	2.7 m3/week	3.8 m3/week	5.5 m3/week	7.4 m3/week	
 Temperate Climate 15 - 23 °C	 Daily feeding: cow manure	35 L or Kg/day	50 L or Kg/day	65 L or Kg/day	100 L or Kg/day	135 L or Kg/day	200 L or Kg/day	265 L or Kg/day	
	 Daily biogas production	1.3 m3/day	1.8 m3/day	2.3 m3/day	3.6 m3/day	4.9 m3/day	7.2 m3/day	9.6 m3/day	
	 Daily cooking time on 1 burner	2.6 Hr/day	3.6 Hr/day	4.6 Hr/day	7.2 Hr/day	9.8 Hr/day	14.4 Hr/day	19.2 Hr/day	
	 Weekly biofertilizer production	0.7 m3/week	1.1 m3/week	1.4 m3/week	2.1 m3/week	2.8 m3/week	4.2 m3/week	5.6 m3/week	
 Cold Climate 12 - 15 °C	 Daily feeding: cow manure	25 L or Kg/day	35 L or Kg/day	45 L or Kg/day	65 L or Kg/day	90 L or Kg/day	135 L or Kg/day	180 L or Kg/day	
	 Daily biogas production	0.8 m3/day	1.2 m3/day	1.5 m3/day	2.2 m3/day	3 m3/day	4.5 m3/day	6 m3/day	
	 Daily cooking time on 1 burner	1.6 Hr/day	2.4 Hr/day	3 Hr/day	4.4 Hr/day	6 Hr/day	9 Hr/day	12 Hr/day	
	 Weekly biofertilizer production	0.5 m3/week	0.7 m3/week	0.9 m3/week	1.4 m3/week	1.9 m3/week	2.8 m3/week	3.8 m3/week	